

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON
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DEPARTMENT OF TOWN PLANNING
M. PHIL.THESIS

**SOCIO-SPATIAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF THESSALONIKA WITHIN-THE-
-WALLS (1890-1988)**

PART B

M A P S A N D P H O T O E S

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CHAPTER III

Map 1. Extra-Ottoman-Empire Commerce in the 19th century.

Map 2. Intra-Ottoman-Empire Commerce in the 19th century.

Map 3. The growth of the city.

Zone I: social strata I, II, III
 Zone II: " " II, III
 Zone III: " " IV
 Zone IV: " " VI and V

social strata I: upper income class
 " " II: lower-upper income class
 " " III: middle income class
 " " IV: low income class
 " " V: lower middle class

Source: V. Petrukidou-Gastlowry, 1986.

Map 4. Modern Thessalonika. Social class distribution.

Map 4. Map of the General Ottoman Staff in 1882-83 (first published by Eyice and republished by A Samouelides-Stephanides). different patterns of the initial orthogonal Plan of the city are visible between Eg-natia St. and Kassandrou St. there are different urban tissues at the area by the coast and 'Ano Polis'

Map 5. Thessalonika in the beginning of the 20th century.

Map 6. Late 19th century - market area.

Fig. 16. Intra-muros quarters in late 19th cent.

- Turkish districts upto 1912 (replaced by Greeks)
- Greek districts
- Jewish "
- Muslim "
- district centre (religious/social)

Map 8a. The public-space network

Map 8b. The old (jewish) quarters replanned in 1891.

Map 9 .Part of the old Plan of Panagia- Laodigitria area. (Published by Ap. Papayanopoulos in 'Monuments of Thessalonika'). The discreet relationship between the monument and the urban tissue is apparent.

Map 11. Planning intervention between 1866-1900.

Map. 12. First and second sector of 'pyrcafstos' zone.
On the left the pre-1890-fire urban tissue.

Map 13. Interventions in the urban tissue between 1866-1900.

Map 14. a. The area burnt in 1890
b. The new plan of the burnt area.

Map 15. The old and the new urban tissues superimposed.

fig 16 a. Building block replanned
 b. " " with aligned its boundaries
 c. " " unaffected.

Map 17. The burnt area and its sectors (Act 2633/1921).

Map 18. Mawson's project for Thessalonika, January 1918.

Map 19. Ernest Hébrard's project for the Universal Centre, 1912.

Map 20. E. Hébrard's project, 1918 (Ancel, 1930).

Map 20. THESSALY 5.
 The Neoclassical
 Plan.

Map 21. Thessalonika in 1929. Approved Plan.

Map 22. E. Hébrard's final proposal in 1921.

Map 23. The new plots in 'pyrikafstos' zone. There can be distinguished the new building blocks and the arranged plots coming out of the replanned urban space.

Fig. 24. The monumental axis from the Aristotelous sq. up to St. Demetrius church.

Fig. 25. The monumental square.

Fig. 26. E. Hébrard's proposal for the Arch and the Town Hall.

Fig. 27. The bazars.

1910
1920

Fig. 28. Thessalonika before and after its planning intervention, the shifts in the historical centre.

Fig. 29. Third sector, financial centre. New and old building blocks.

Map 30. The public space network in the Neoclassical Plan.

Map 31. THESSUP 5. Retailing in the broader urban complex.

Map 36 THESSUP 5. Land Uses.

Map 36 THESSUP 5. Existing conditions (commerce, manufacture).

